

**METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE NOUN PHRASE CATEGORY:
ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING IN STUDENTS**

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Abstract. *This thesis explores effective methodologies for teaching the noun phrase category to students, aiming to enhance their language learning abilities. The article discusses various strategies, activities, and instructional approaches that can be employed by educators to facilitate students' understanding and mastery of noun phrases. By employing a well-rounded methodology, teachers can create engaging and interactive learning experiences that promote students' language acquisition and communication skills.*

Keywords: *noun phrase, methodology, teaching, language learning, students, instructional approaches, language acquisition, communication skills.*

**МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ КАТЕГОРИИ ИМЕННЫХ ФРАЗ:
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКУ СТУДЕНТОВ**

Аннотация. *В диссертации исследуются эффективные методики обучения студентов категории именных словосочетаний с целью повышения их способностей к изучению языка. В статье обсуждаются различные стратегии, виды деятельности и учебные подходы, которые могут быть использованы преподавателями для облегчения понимания и усвоения учащимися словосочетаний с существительными. Используя всестороннюю методологию, учителя могут создавать увлекательные и интерактивные учебные программы, которые способствуют овладению учащимися языковыми навыками и коммуникативными навыками.*

Ключевые слова: *именное словосочетание, методика, обучение, изучение языка, студенты, подходы к обучению, овладение языком, коммуникативные навыки.*

The study of the noun phrase category is an essential part of language learning for students. This category plays a crucial role in developing students' abilities to comprehend, express, and communicate ideas effectively. In this article, we will discuss a comprehensive methodology for teaching the noun phrase category in Uzbek, focusing on strategies and approaches that enhance students' language learning experience. By implementing these methodologies, educators can foster students' understanding and mastery of noun phrases, enabling them to become proficient users of the Uzbek language.

Teaching the noun phrase category requires a systematic and engaging methodology. Here, we outline a step-by-step approach that can be adopted by educators to effectively teach noun phrases to students:

At this stage, students learn to recognize objects and words by their names. Emphasis is placed on the lexical meaning of words, and students develop the skill to group words based on their meanings. Grouping exercises based on the lexical meaning of words help students compare and identify similarities, thereby fostering abstract thinking.

In this stage, students learn to distinguish nouns that answer the question "who" or "what." They identify words that serve as answers to these questions. This stage enhances students' ability to differentiate words based on interrogations and cultivates their grammatical thinking skills.

Additionally, students begin to recognize and write nouns with the appropriate letter changes (e.g., plural forms).

To develop a comprehensive understanding of noun phrases, students need to categorize them into lexical groups. Teachers introduce words denoting objects early in the lessons and identify common signs that are applicable to all noun phrases. By answering questions related to these words, students grasp the concept of noun phrases. To emphasize the significance of noun phrases in speech, teachers can select texts from reading materials and instruct students to identify and read them without noun phrases. By experiencing the impact of noun phrase omission on text comprehension, students realize the indispensability of noun phrases in effective communication.

In the 2nd grade, students deepen their knowledge of noun meanings, proverbs, and related nouns. They are introduced to singular and plural forms of nouns, learning to differentiate between them by meaning and suffix. Students develop skills to convert singular nouns to plural and vice versa, considering the connection of words in sentences and using nouns correctly in speech. The topic of possessive suffixes may be complex for elementary students. Teachers can begin by explaining the lexical meaning of the word "possessive" to help students understand the concept of ownership. Students learn that possessive suffixes indicate ownership and establish a connection between the noun and its possessor. Through analysis and exercises, students become familiar with the composition and usage of possessive suffixes.

In language, there are three persons: the speaker or 1st person, the listener or 2nd person, and others or 3rd person. As I speak to you now, explaining the topic, I am the speaker (1st person), and you are the listener. This means there are others who are not currently participating in the conversation. They are considered the 3rd person. Nouns can be applied in singular and plural forms. It is known that something can belong to one person or to two or more people. The possessive suffixes attached to the noun indicate that an object belongs to one of the three persons in either unity or plurality. For example, the suffix -im added to the word "my book," as you have identified, indicates that the book refers to the 1st person, meaning the owner of the book is the 1st person. (The suffixes -im, -ing, and -I are also explained in the same way.) From this, we can draw the conclusion that these suffixes added to nouns are called possessive suffixes, and they indicate possession.

Possessive suffixes are added to nouns in two different forms: to nouns ending with a vowel (-m, -ing, -si), and to nouns ending with a consonant (-im, -ing, -I, -imiz, -ngiz, -si). After that, the students read the rule in the "Uzbek Language" textbook and analyze the table.

Exercises such as finding a noun applied with a possessive suffix from the text, analyzing it based on its composition, determining the number of persons indicated by the possessive suffix, adding a possessive suffix to the given noun in the text, and stating which person or persons the subject belongs to, are conducted. The study of possessive suffixes does not end there. In the process of studying noun agreement, a noun with a possessive suffix is associated with another noun. Similarly, in the process of studying possessive pronoun agreement, a noun with a possessive suffix is associated with the possessive pronoun. This provides knowledge about vocabulary formation.

Agreement expresses the relationship between nouns and other words in a sentence. This means that when changing agreements, students understand the connection between words in a sentence. Work on stems begins after students learn to distinguish between meaning and

grammatically linked syllables in a sentence. Working on words also involves working on the connection between words in a sentence.

Conclusion. To understand the words, readers must know exactly which word the noun is associated with in the sentence. The change of a noun in a sentence with suffixes along with other words is observed much earlier. In fact, students are practically familiar with the change in word forms from Grade 1, but they may not know what a word form is. Children are introduced to form-making (word-shifting) suffixes in the next grade, which they understand serve to connect words in a sentence.

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